

LC-MS Instrumentation; Vast applications; Newer approaches

Kakarla Vineela

University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Acharya Nagarjuna University, kakinada, Andhrapradesh, 533434

ABSTRACT

Here new approaches of LC-MS were discussed. And also covers LC-MS in various sections like instrumentation parts, like light source, eg: Ion Source, Electrospray ionisation source, Atmosphere Pressure Chemical ionisation source, Atmosphere Pressure Photo-ionisation, and analyzers like quadrapole Analyzers, Time of flight Analyzers, Ion trap Analyzers. And finally detect the analyzing compound through detector. And in these chromatography some must be 1ml/min, normalized flow rate in the range of 0.05-0.2 ml /min that enhance sensitivity. And mobile phase also plays a crucial role in selecting the suitable mobile phase. For both normal and reverse phase LC like H₂O, C₂H₃N, CH₃OH, CH₃CH₂OH, CHCl₃, are susceptible with ESI, water is conventional for separation, but for only specific compounds only. It also has a vast applications in analytical department. In also analysis of various protein determination, research field, clinical trials, areas & screening new borne, therapeutic drug monitoring and analyzing drug of abuse & metabolites & hormones. It has a wound healing function, quantification of oligonucleotides ‘‘ LC-MS Instrumentation Vast applications & Newer approaches’’.

Keywords: Oligonucleotides, Electrospray ionisation source, Atmosphere pressure chemical ionisation, Atmospheric Photo ionisation, Quadrapole Analysers.

INTRODUCTION

Liquid Chromatography -Mass spectrometry is a Hyphenated technique that works Liquid chromatography along with the detection of mass spectrophotometer. LC-MS combined separating hplc and detect the mass spectrometer chromatography generally consists of a mobile phase. Eg: Ethanol, Acetonitrile, stationary phase eg: Column made with very tiny particles). In mass spectrometer that determine the mass and charge ratio of ion particles.

Instrumentation:

The simple affordable components of LC-MS makes high efficient & accurate results. Ion source such as ESI, APCI & APPI (Atmospheric Pressure photo ionization) have facilitated the analyse of pharmaceutical compounds including non-volatile & polar or non polar molecules with less molecule

weights. Mass analyzers such as ion trap (IT), Quadrapole (Q), orbitrap & time of flight (TOF).

Mass Spectrometry:

Ion Sources

Electrospray ionisation source

Fenn achieved the source which turns into robust ion source. ESI good with the polar compounds. Liquid samples are injected through a metal capillary constant at 3 to 5 Kv and form a tiny drops at the end of the capillary, it converts into charged particles. The capillary must be orthogonal when enter the mass spectrophotometer in order to prevent impurities. The droplets are dissolve when apply of temperature and nitrogen gas, and the electric charge on the droplets is passing through the analytes. Then the ionized compounds are then transfer to the large vaccum of the mass spectrophotometer via small apertures. Here

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the ion source is to detect positive or negative charges, and in this way instrument run will be performed.

Atmospheric Pressure chemical ionisation source

In atmospheric pressure chemical ionisation (APCI), as with ESI, liquid is passing through a capillary and forms small droplets at the tip. From beginning gas, liquid molecules in the ion source, react with the analyte and ionisation occurs. While steroids are neutral compounds therefore APCI has been used to determine the free steroids. This technique also analyse the high fats.

Atmospheric pressure photo -ionisation

Atmospheric pressure photo-ionisation (APPI) through photons to excite and ionisation after nebulisation. This is also apply in analyse of single charge ions and also for neutral compounds.

Analysers:

Quadrapole Analysers

The quadrapole analyser contains of a four parallel metal rods. Applying radiofrequency voltages causes the transmit of a narrow band of m/z values with the axis of the rods. Difference in frequency and time it can be scan in the range of m/z values, resulting a mass spectrum. Mostly the analyzer operates at less than 4000 m/z per second, the mass accuracy of unit mass resolution is greater than 0.1 m/z . Ions are converted into fragments by collisions mixing with nitrogen gas this process is called collision. Cell is a quadrapole is to maintain the low pressure for dissociation of fragment ions are produced. A Collision cell is placed between two quadrapole mass analysers. This combination is called a triple quadrapole mass spectrometer it is a tandem MS in this two or more stages of mass analysis are individually applied.

Time of flight Analysers:

The time of flight (TOF) analyser control by accelerating ions through a high voltage. The difference between the velocity of the ions & to reach the detector, based upon the m/z values. It has high

sensitivity. It is easily to determine for small molecules.

Ion trap Analyzers:

Ion trap analyzers is in a 3 dimensional space by radio frequency voltages. Ion are ejected from the trap by the m/z values. Inert gas is pumped to the trap to enhance fragmentation. In ion trap analyzers they do fragment & separation of ions occurs, before the occurs of M.S. spectrum. So this called Ion capabilities.

Liquid Chromatography:

Flow rate:

ESI source generally handle flow rates up to 1ml/min, low flow rates in the range of 0.05-0.02ml/min results in increased sensitivity. Column diameter with 1.0 or 2.1 mm diameter are well suitable for direct coupling with these ion source. These separations are useful in the proteomics area where high sensitivity & resolution are required to

Mobile phase reverse & normal phase LC: H_2O , C_2H_3N , CH_3OH , C_2H_6O , $CHCl_3$ are compatible with ESI. Water is mostly used as solvent for LC-MS but only specific compounds only. Because the solvent must be pure doesn't contain traces it can effect the quality of lc-ms measurable.

Applications:

LC-MS also increases the reproducibility of protein analysis particularly in immune capture, digestion & clean up steps, essential for large scale sample processing. Instrument selection includes mass spectrometers like triple quadrapole(Q9Q) & high resolution mass spectrometer greatly impacts assay performance. LC-MS is widely used in research & clinical trials areas, & its applications is gradually increasing. LC-MS /MS in clinical testing include screening new borne, therapeutic drug monitoring & indentifying drugs of abuse & metabolites & hormones. LC-TOF MS/MS – also identify the metabolites in plant extract.

It also predicts the wound healing function in the herbal extracts like (eg: Oroxyllum indicum (I). Kurz

LC-MS is a tool that is also useful in quantification of oligonucleotides that is key role in their biological roles & diagnosis. MALAT-1 Anti sense oligo nucleotides making it a important tool for rapid screening & discovery.

Newer Advances in LC-MS technique:

API Sources for magnetic sector instruments:

The difficulty arises when coupling an API source to a instrument to high acceleration voltage and have high pressure between ion source and analyzer, sometimes leads to a electrical breakdown, extensive collision activation of ions. So magnetic be preferred.

API Sources for fourier -transform ion – cyclotron resonance instruments:

An electrospray ion source for FT-ICR-MS instrument has first discovered by Henry et al. 146,147,148. The efficient tandem mass spectrometry helps in high – resolution measurements. The FT-ICR-MS is a more extended analytical use.

API Sources for time -of -flight instruments:

In these combination 3 basic instrumental designs are proposed that are: 1) An electrospray Source on x-axis with the TOF analyzer, 2) an electrospray source perpendicular to the direction of acceleration of ions into the TOF analyzer and (3) an electrospray source coupled to the ion -trap storage device, positioned on -axis with a reflectron TOF analyzer, and an electrospray source coupled to the ion -trap storage device, positioned on -axis with a reflectron TOF analyzer.

LC-MS via MALDI-TOF

The achievement of LC-MS via MALDI is processed. They are two methods under investigation.

Here the Continuous -flow type interface, and the similar to the continuous- flow fast-atom bombardment.

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